

NEW SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF AZITHROMYCIN IN PURE AND DOSAGE FORMS USING N-BROMOSUCCINIMIDE AND POTASSIUM PERMANGANATE AS OXIDANTS

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ABSTRACT

Two simple, rapid, accurate, sensitive and economical visible spectrophotometric (indirect) methods (A and B) for the determination of azithromycin (AZT) in bulk sample and in dosage forms are described. The first method is based on the oxidation of the drug by N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) and determination of the unreacted NBS by measurement of the decrease in absorbance of methyl orange dye (MO) at a suitable $\lambda_{\max} = 507$ nm. The absorbance concentration plot is linear over the range (0.2-4.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$). The second method is based on oxidation of AZT by potassium permanganate in acidic medium, and

determination of the unreacted oxidant by measuring the decrease in absorbance using three different dyes; methylene blue (MB), orange G (OG) and malachite green dye (MG) at a suitable λ_{\max} (660, 475 and 617 nm), respectively. Regression analysis of Beer's law plots showed good correlation in the concentration ranges (0.4-38, 0.8-22 and 0.6-16 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), respectively. The quality control/assurance parameters such as limits of detection (LOD), quantification (LOQ), molar absorptivity and Sandelle's sensitivity values are also reported. The accuracy and precision of the methods were studied on intra-day and inter-day basis. No interference was observed from common pharmaceutical additives. The methods are used successfully to assay AZT in its pharmaceutical dosage forms viz. tablets and capsules.

KEY WORDS: Azithromycin; Spectrophotometric; Redox reaction; N-bromosuccinimide; Potassium permanganate; Pharmaceutical analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Azithromycin, chemically, (2R,3S,4R,5R,8R,10R,11R,12S,13S,14R)-2-ethyl-3, 4, 10-

trihydroxy-3, 5, 6, 8, 10, 12,14-heptamethyl-15-oxo-11-[[3,4,6-trideoxy-3-(dimethylamino)- β -D-xylo-]oxy]-1-oxa-6-azacyclo-pentadec-13-yl-2,6-dideoxy-3-C-methyl-3-O-methyl- α -L-ribo-hexopyranoside is a semi-synthetic macrolide antibiotic widely used in the respiratory tract infections, like pharyngitis, pneumonia, chronic bronchitis, bronchopneumonia, skin and soft tissue infections and some sexually transmitted diseases, that acts on Gram positive bacteria and Gram negative bacteria ^[1]. The most commonly used techniques for the determination of azithromycin in pharmaceutical dosage forms are high performance liquid chromatography ^[2, 3], liquid chromatography-mass spectrometry ^[4], microbiological ^[5], differential pulse voltammetric ^[6-8], amperometric ^[9] diffuse reflectance near infrared spectroscopy ^[10] and spectrophotometric methods ^[11-16].

However, chromatographic techniques require long experimental procedures for sample clean up and demand expensive equipment. In differential pulse voltammetric method, the adsorption of the drug on the electrode surface has not been sufficiently strong and hence it has not been analytically useful. Lakshmi ^[11] have reported a visible spectrophotometric method for the determination azithromycin in tablets is not specific. Most of the reported methods are highly sophisticated, costly and time-consuming.

The objective of the present work was to develop a simple spectrophotometric method for the determination of azithromycin in pharmaceutical formulations. The present procedure neither requires any extraction nor any elaborate equipment and the method is less time-consuming. Spectrophotometry is considered as the most convenient analytical technique in pharmaceutical analysis because of its inherent simplicity and availability in most quality control laboratories ^[17-21]. However, AZT does not possess any chromophore in its molecule, which is the essential requirement for the direct or indirect spectrophotometric analysis.

The oxidation reaction between NBS or KMnO₄ in acidic medium and AZT have not been investigated yet but for other drugs ^[22-25]. Therefore, the present study was devoted to explore NBS and KMnO₄ as an oxidant in the development of two (direct and indirect) selective and sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of AZT in tablets and capsules. The present work describes two spectrophotometric methods which are superior to the reported ones, for rapidity, reproducibility, time consuming and high sensitivity. The proposed methods which used are well known for their high absorptivity and they will have been utilized for estimation of oxidant (NBS and potassium permanganate) in acidic medium. Where modern and expensive apparatus such as GLC, HPLC and HPTLC are not available.

EXPERIMENTAL

Apparatus

All the spectral measurement were made using double-beam UV/Vis spectrophotometer (Biotech Engineering Ltd., UK), with wavelength range 190 –1100 nm, spectral bandwidth 2.0 nm, with scanning speed 400 nm/min, equipped with 10 mm matched quartz cells. A thermostat water bath, Buchi 461 water bath, Schwiz (France) was used to carry out the temperature studies and Magnetic Mix. 100, Thermo Scientific, UK,

Materials and reagents

All reagents and chemicals used were of analytical or pharmaceutical grade and all solutions were freshly prepared daily in doubly distilled water.

- Pure Azithromycin dihydrate bulk powder was obtained from Egyptian Organization for Control and Pharmaceutical Research-Egypt. AZT working solution was prepared by dissolving 0.02 g of pure AZT in 50 ml of bidistilled water and complete to 100 ml with bidistilled water to obtain the working standard solution of 200 µg/ml, store the prepared solution at room temperature.
- Aqueous solutions of dyes (1.0×10^{-3} M) methyl orange (MO) (Merck), (1.0×10^{-4} M) methylene blue (MB) (Merck), (1.0×10^{-3} M) orange G (OG) and (1.0×10^{-4} M) malachite green (MG) (Merck) were prepared by dissolving in an appropriate weight in 100 ml bidistilled water.
- A stock solution of 1.0×10^{-3} M NBS (Aldrich Co., Ltd., Gillingham-Dorst, Germany) was freshly prepared by dissolving 0.0177 g of NBS in a least amount of warm water in a 100 ml measuring flask and then diluted with distilled water to the mark.
- A stock (1.0×10^{-3} M) solution of KMnO_4 (Aldrich), was freshly prepared by dissolving an accurate weight in bidistilled water, and standardized ^[26].
- A 2.0 M of HCl was prepared by adding exact volume from stock concentrated acid to bidistilled water in 500 ml measuring flask (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany, sp. gr. 1.18%, 37%) to 100 ml with distilled water.
- A solution of 2.0 M H_2SO_4 , was prepared by adding exact volume from stock (98%) concentrated acid to bidistilled water in 500 ml measuring flask, and standardized as recorded ^[27].

General procedure

For the first method, (method A) depends on oxidation of AZT by addition of 0.01-0.65 ml AZT ($100 \mu\text{g/ml}$) to 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M NBS containing 0.5 ml HCl, 2.0 M. The solution was heated in a water bath at 80 ± 1 °C for 5.0 min. The solution was cooled and 0.9 ml (1.0×10^{-3} M) of MO was added, the volume was completed to 10 ml with bidistilled water. For the second method (method B) depends on oxidation of AZT by addition of 0.01-4.5 ml AZT ($200 \mu\text{g/ml}$) to 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M KMnO_4 containing 1.0 and 1.2 ml of 2.0 M H_2SO_4 was added on using MB, OG respectively, and 1.0 ml of 0.2 M H_2SO_4 was added on using MG. The solution was heated in a water bath at 80 ± 1 °C for 6.0, 4.0 and 5.0 min, the mixture of acidic solution was cooled and 1.1 ml (1.0×10^{-4} M) of MB, 1.8 ml (1.0×10^{-3} M) of OG and, 2.0 ml (1.0×10^{-4} M) of MG was added, the volume was completed to 10 ml with bidistilled water. The decrease in color intensity of dye was measured spectrophotometrically against a blank solution containing the same constituent except drug treated similarly, at their corresponding λ_{max} 507 (method A) 660, 475 and 617 nm (method B), respectively. The concentration range was determined in each case by plotting the concentration of AZT against absorbance at the corresponding maximum wavelengths.

Figure 1: Molar ratio method for AZT (1.0×10^{-3} M) using NBS and KMnO_4 (1.0×10^{-3} M) and dyes, MO and OG (1.0×10^{-3} M) but MB and MG (1.0×10^{-4} M).

Stoichiometric relationship

The stoichiometry of the reaction between AZT and the oxidant at the selected conditions was established by the molar ratio method. In this method 1.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M NBS (method

A) 1.0×10^{-3} M KMnO_4 (method B) is kept constant and variable concentrations (0.1-4.0 ml) of AZT (1.0×10^{-3} M) were added. The absorbance was measured at λ_{max} against blank solution prepared in the same manner. The absorbance values were then plotted against the molar ratio [D]/[O] as shown in Figure 1.

Procedure for dosage forms

Twenty tablets/capsules, were carefully evacuated; their contents were weighed and finely powdered. An accurately weighed quantity of the capsule contents equivalent to 20 mg of AZT was transferred into a 100 ml calibrated flask, and dissolved in about 40 ml of distilled water and sulphuric acid (0.2 ml, 2.0 M). The contents of the flask were swirled, sonicated for 5.0 min, and then completed to volume with water. The contents were mixed well and filtered (through Whatman No. 41 filter paper) rejecting the first portion of the filtrate. The prepared solution was diluted quantitatively with distilled water to obtain a suitable concentration for the analysis; the analysis was carried out in triplicate for three pharmaceutical dosage forms i.e. tablets and capsules. The results of analysis of pharmaceutical dosage forms are shown in (Table 2). The good recovery confirmed the accuracy and the specificity of the proposed method, and the lack of interference from the common excipients, and colorant/preservatives, used in the manufacture of tablets and capsules.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

First Method (A)

The proposed spectrophotometric methods are based on the reaction between AZT and measured excess of NBS and subsequent determination of the latter by reacting it with a fixed amount of MO dye, and measuring the absorbance at 507 nm. The reaction takes place completely after 5.0 min., was heated in a thermostat water bath at 80 ± 1 °C. This method make use of the bleaching action of NBS on the dye, the decolorization being caused by the oxidative destruction of the dye. AZT when added in increasing concentrations to a fixed concentration of NBS consumes the latter and there will be a concomitant decrease in the concentration of NBS. When a fixed concentration of dye is added to decreasing concentrations of NBS, a concomitant increase in the concentration of dye is obtained. Consequently, a proportional increase in the absorbance at the respective λ_{max} is observed with increasing concentrations of AZT, the color remains constant for at least 48 h.

Second Method (B)

The method involves two steps namely:

- Oxidation of AZT with KMnO_4 in acidic medium by heating in water bath 80 ± 1 °C.
- Determination of unreacted oxidant by measuring the decrease in absorbance of dyes at a suitable λ_{max} .

(Violet)

(Colorless)

The influence of each of the following variables on the reaction was tested.

Effect of NBS concentration

The influence of NBS concentration was studied in the range from 10^{-4} - 10^{-2} M, as final concentration. The optimum results were obtained with 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M.

Effect of permanganate concentration

The influence of potassium permanganate concentration was studied in the range from 10^{-4} - 10^{-2} M, as final concentration. The optimum results were obtained with 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M; higher concentration of KMnO_4 caused the color to be disturbed.

Figure 2: Effect of ml added of HCl (method A) (2.0 M) on absorbance of 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of AZT with NBS (1.0×10^{-3} M) and MO (1.0×10^{-3} M), sulphuric acid 2.0 M (for method B) on absorbance of 15.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of AZT with KMnO_4 (1.0×10^{-3} M) with dyes MB, OG and (0.2 M) with MG dye.

Effect of medium

The different types of acid were examined (HCl, HClO₄, H₂SO₄, H₃PO₄, CH₃COOH and HNO₃). The most suitable acid to achieve maximum yield of redox reaction was found to be 0.5 ml of 2.0 M HCl for (method A) and 1.0 and 1.2 ml of 2.0 M H₂SO₄ was added on using MB, OG respectively, and 1.0 ml of 0.2 M H₂SO₄ using MG, for (method B) Figure 2.

Effect of temperature and time

The reaction takes place completely after 20 min at room temperature 25±1 °C. The oxidation process of AZT with NBS is catalyzed by heating in a thermostat water bath at 80±1 °C for 5.0 min, to produce a water-soluble bluish-green colored species. The oxidation process of AZT for the (method B) KMnO₄ in acidic medium was catalyzed by heating in a thermostat water bath of 80±1 °C for 6.0, 4.0 and 5.0 min, using MB, OG and MG, respectively. After oxidation process, the solution must be cooled at least for 2.0 min before addition of dye.

Effect of sequence of additions

The effect of sequence of additions on the oxidation process of AZT was studied by measuring the absorbance of solution prepared by different sequence of additions against a blank solution prepared in the same manner. Experiments showed that (Oxidant-Acid-Drug) for both methods, gave the best results.

Effect of dye concentration

The optimum volume of dye used for production of maximum color intensity was 0.9 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M MO for (method A), 1.1 ml of 1.0×10^{-4} M MB, 1.8 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M of OG and 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-4} M of MG, for (method B). The effect of time after the addition of dye indicated that shaking for 1.0 min was sufficient to give reliable results for all dyes. The color remains constant for at least 24 h.

Stoichiometric ratio

The stoichiometry of the reaction between AZT and the oxidant at the selected conditions was established by the molar ratio method. In this method 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M NBS for (method A), 2.0 ml of 1.0×10^{-3} M KMnO₄ for (method B) is kept constant and variable concentrations (0.1 - 4.0 ml) of AZT (1.0×10^{-3} M) were added using micropipette. The absorbance was measured at λ_{\max} against blank solution prepared in the same manner. The absorbance values were then plotted against the molar ratio [D]/[O]. The stoichiometry of [D]/[O] at the selected conditions showed that the inflection of the two straight lines at 0.6 for

(method A) 1.53, 0.51 and 0.54 using MB, OG and MG, respectively for (method B), Figure 1.

Analytical data

Beer's law limits, molar absorptivities, Sandell sensitivities, regression equations and correlation coefficients were calculated and recorded. The limits of detection ($K=3$) and quantitation ($K=10$) were established according to IUPAC definitions [27] are recorded in Table 1. In order to determine the accuracy and precision of the methods, solution containing three different concentrations of AZT were prepared and analyzed in six replicates. The analytical results obtained from this investigation were summarized in Table 2.

Table 1: Optical and regression characteristics of AZT for the proposed methods.

Parameters	(Method A) NBS (MO)	(Method B) $KMnO_4$ in acidic medium		
		(MB)	(OG)	(MG)
λ_{max} nm	507	660	475	617
Stability / h	24	72	72	48
Heating time (min.)	5.0	5.0	4.0	6.0
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.2 - 4.5	0.4 - 38.0	0.8 - 22.0	0.6 - 16.0
Ringbom limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.3 - 4.1	0.6 - 37.8	0.9 - 21.7	0.8 - 15.7
Molar absorptivity ($\text{l} / \text{mol.cm}$)	13.74×10^4	2.90×10^4	3.53×10^4	3.30×10^4
Sandell sensitivity (ng/cm)	5.71	27.03	22.22	23.81
Detection limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.069	0.033	0.054	0.062
Quantitation limits ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.32	0.33	0.18	0.21
Regression equation*: Slope (b)	0.175	0.037	0.045	0.042
RSD% of slope	0.0053	0.0035	0.0032	0.0043
Intercept (a)	-0.0020	0.0059	-0.0009	-0.0067
RSD% of intercept	0.0044	0.0025	0.0029	0.0033
Stoichiometric ratio	1 : 0.60	1 : 1.53	1 : 0.51	1 : 0.54
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9998	0.9999
RSD** %	0.72	0.48	0.39	0.59

* $A = a + bC$ where C is concentration of drug in $\mu\text{g/ml}$ and A is absorbance.

** Relative standard deviation for six determinations.

Interference

A systematic quantitative study was undertaken by measuring the absorbance of solutions containing 2.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of AZT for method A or 15 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of AZT for method B with varying concentration of the additives and excipients such as cellulose, talc powder, lactose, calcium hydrogen phosphate, magnesium stearate, micro-crystalline cellulose and starch. Under the

experimental conditions, the effect of excipients frequently found in formulations was evaluated using the proposed method; the excipients in all tablets and capsules are not interfere.

Table 2: Evaluation of the accuracy and precision of the proposed methods for AZT.

Reagents		Taken µg/ml	Recovery %	RSD ^a %	RE ^b %	Confidence limits ^c
NBS	MO	2.0	100.5	0.91	0.98	2.01 ± 0.0197
		3.0	100.3	0.67	0.81	3.01 ± 0.0243
		4.0	99.8	0.59	0.89	3.99 ± 0.0357
KMnO ₄	MB	10.0	99.8	0.87	1.10	9.98 ± 0.1101
		20.0	100.1	0.79	0.70	20.02 ± 0.1398
		30.0	99.9	0.46	0.66	29.97 ± 0.1998
	OG	5.0	100.2	0.80	1.02	5.01 ± 0.0512
		10.0	99.6	0.55	0.97	9.96 ± 0.0968
		15.0	99.9	0.66	0.68	14.98 ± 0.1024
	MG	4.0	100.5	0.80	1.04	4.02 ± 0.0418
		8.0	99.5	0.46	0.93	7.96 ± 0.0737
		12.0	99.8	0.61	0.75	11.98 ± 0.0901

^a Relative standard deviation for six determinations.

^b Relative error.

^c 95 % confidence limits and five degrees of freedom.

Method validation

The proposed methods were successfully applied to determine AZT in its dosage forms. The accuracy of the proposed methods is evaluated by applying standard addition technique, in which variable amounts of the drug were added to the previously analyzed portion of pharmaceutical preparations. The results recorded in Table 3, were compared statistically with the official method ^[28] by Student's t-test (for accuracy), and variance ratio F-test (for precision) ^[29], at 95% confidence level as recorded in Table 4. The results showed that the t- and F- values were lower than the critical values indicating that there was no significant difference between the proposed and official methods. The proposed method was more accurate with high recoveries compared to the official method. So the proposed methods can be recommended for routine analysis of AZT in pure and pharmaceutical forms, i.e. tablets and capsules in the majority of drug quality control laboratories.

Table 3: Determination of AZT in tablets and capsules using standard addition technique.

Samples	Method A (NBS)			Method B (KMnO ₄)					
	(MO)			(MB)		(OG)		(MG)	
	Taken 3.0 µg/ml			Taken 20.0 µg/ml		Taken 10.0 µg/ml		Taken 8.0 µg/ml	
	Added µg/ml	Found* µg/ml	Recovery %	Found* µg/ml	Recovery %	Found* µg/ml	Recovery %	Found* µg/ml	Recovery %
Zithrokan ^a 500 mg / Capsule	0.0	3.02	100.66	19.99	99.95	10.01	100.10	8.01	100.13
	1.0	3.97	99.25	20.96	99.81	10.99	99.90	8.99	99.89
	2.0	4.95	99.00	22.02	100.09	11.98	99.83	9.98	99.80
	3.0	5.97	99.5	23.01	100.04	13.01	100.08	11.01	100.09
Azithromycin ^b 250 mg / Tablet	0.0	3.01	100.33	19.95	99.75	10.02	100.20	8.02	100.25
	1.0	4.02	100.50	21.01	100.04	11.01	100.09	8.97	99.67
	2.0	4.96	99.60	22.02	100.09	11.94	99.50	9.96	99.60
	3.0	6.02	100.33	22.95	99.78	13.02	100.15	11.02	100.18
Zomax ^c 500 mg / Capsule	0.0	2.97	99.00	19.97	99.85	09.95	99.50	7.96	99.50
	1.0	3.97	99.25	20.94	99.71	10.97	99.72	8.97	99.67
	2.0	4.96	99.20	21.94	99.77	11.97	99.75	9.96	99.60
	3.0	5.99	99.83	23.02	100.09	12.96	99.69	10.96	99.63

* Average of six determinations.

^a Hikma Pharma S.A.E., 6th of October City – Egypt.

^b Akums Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Ltd. – India.

^c Fabrique Par Les Laboratoires Ibn Al-Baytar, Carthage, Tunis, Hikma Pharmaceuticals – Jordanie.

Table 4: Determination of AZT in pharmaceutical formulations using the proposed and official methods.

Parameter	NBS (MO)	Method B (KMnO ₄)			Official
		MB	OG	MG	
Zithrokan 500 mg / Capsule¹					
Recovery % ^a	100.1 ± 1.11	100.2 ± 1.1	99.8 ± 0.29	99.9 ± 0.9	99.5 ± 1.0
± Standard Deviation	0.76	0.66	0.96	1.01	1.11
Number of experiments	6	6	6	6	6
Variance	0.71	0.73	0.50	0.57	1.17
Student t-value ^b	1.87	1.93	0.84	1.03	1.47
Variance ratio F-test ^b	1.82	1.72	2.56	3.18	2.42
Azithromycin 250 mg / Tablet²					
Recovery % ^a	99.8 ± 1.2	99.8 ± 0.71	99.7 ± 1.1	100.1 ± 0.72	99.3 ± 0.81
± Standard Deviation	0.66	0.79	0.71	0.74	0.93
Number of experiments	6	6	6	6	6
Variance	0.69	0.57	0.53	0.43	1.12
Student t-value ^b	0.82	0.69	0.82	0.83	1.20
Variance ratio F-test ^b	2.0	1.71	2.07	1.79	2.16

	Zomax 500 mg / Capsule³				
Recovery % ^a	99.4 ± 0.52	100.1 ± 1.1	99.8 ± 0.73	100 ± 1.41	99.2 ± 0.73
± Standard Deviation	1.21	0.99	1.01	0.55	1.26
Number of experiments	6	6	6	6	6
Variance	1.17	0.46	1.06	0.59	1.29
Student t-value ^b	0.76	0.70	1.20	0.76	0.88
Variance ratio F-test ^b	3.12	3.13	3.04	2.66	3.02

^a Recovery %, ^b Theoretical value for t- and F- values for five degrees of freedom and 95 % confidence limits are 2.57 and 5.05, respectively.

¹ Hikma Pharma S.A.E., 6th of October City – Egypt.

² Akums Drugs & Pharmaceuticals Ltd. – India.

³ Fabrique Par Les Laboratoires Ibn Al-Baytar, Carthage, Tunis, Hikma Pharmaceuticals – Jordanie.

CONCLUSIONS

The proposed methods were advantageous over other reported visible spectrophotometric and colorimetric methods, related to their high reproducibility, high sensitivity, less time consuming and using simple and inexpensive reagents. Moreover, these methods allowed the determination of AZT up to 0.2 µg/ml, in addition to simplicity, rapidity, precision and stability of colored species for more than 48 h. The proposed methods may be applied for routine analysis and in quality control laboratories for the quantitative determination of the AZT in raw materials and in pharmaceutical formulations.

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